

WATERAGRI

D8.6: WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board Report

April 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 858735.

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Work Package	WP8
Delivery Date (DoA)	30/04/2021
Actual Delivery Date	30/04/2021
Abstract:	This document details a strategy for the implementation of the Enablers Advisory Board in the WATERAGRI project.

Document Revision History			
Date	Version	Author/Contributor/ Reviewer	Summary of main changes
01/04/2021	1.0	Sebastian Puculek	First draft consulted with the Project Coordinator
05/04/2021	1.0	Suhad Almuktar	First feedback
05/04/2021	1.0	Miklas Scholz	First feedback
09/04/2021	2.0	Sebastian Puculek	Second draft
26/04/2021	2.1	Suhad Almuktar	Quality review
27/04/2021	2.1	Miklas Scholz	Final review
29/04/2021	3.0	Sebastian Puculek	Final version
30/04/2021	3.1	Miklas Scholz	Final version (minor edits)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X

WATERAGRI Consortium			
Participant Number	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	LUNDS UNIVERSITET	ULUND	SE
2	EDEN MICROFLUIDICS	EDEN	FR
3	FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH	FZJ	DE
4	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT Oy	VTT	FI
5	DEBRECENI EGYETEM	UNIDEB	HU
6	ALCHEMIA-NOVA GMBH	ALCN	AT
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8	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	BOKU	AT
9	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	UNIBO	IT
10	THE UNIVERSITY OF SALFORD	USAL	UK
11	COCONSORZIO DI BONIFICA DI SECONDO GRADO PER IL CANALE EMILIANO ROMAGNOLO CANALE GIANDOTTI	CER	IT
12	CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE	CDR	PL
13	INOSENS DOO NOVI SAD	INOSENS	RS
14	UNIWERSYTET PRZYRODNICZY WE WROCLAWIU	UPWr	PL
15	BAY ZOLTAN ALKALMAZOTT KUTATASI KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT	BZN	HU
16	VULTUS AB	VULTUS	SE
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	TU DELFT	NL
18	UNIVERSITE DE NEUCHATEL	UNINE	CH
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Funding Scheme: Research and Innovation Action (RIA) • Theme: SFS-23-2019
Start date of project: 01 May 2020 • Duration: 48 months

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
EAB	Enablers Advisory Board
LUND	Lund University (official WATERAGRI project abbreviation)
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
GA	General Assembly
EB	Executive Board
PC	Project Coordinator

1 Introduction

1.1 The purpose of this deliverable

The Advisory Board plays a crucial role in every complex and multi-stakeholder project. It helps coordination bodies to focus on project goals and often plays an important networking role in helping consortium members to establish valuable connections outside of the project. Through its diversity, it allows us to look at the project objectives from different angles. This deliverable describes the strategic approach of the WATERAGRI project to its Enablers Advisory Board (EAB). The purpose of this deliverable is to shape boundary conditions and strategy for successful cooperation with the members of the WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board (EAB).

1.2 Related documents

1.2.1 Grant Application

The interest in using the Advisory Board in the future project phases was embedded at the very beginning of the WATERAGRI proposal writing. Consortium core members expressed an interest in using an external advisory body (external to the coordination team) in such a complex and multistakeholder project. The concept of the advisory board was consulted with all the consortium partners and initial contacts have been established. In the grant application phase, it has been named the WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board. The importance of having an advisory board on the implementation stage was expressed in the final version of the application by dedicating separate task 8.4 Enablers Advisory Board lead by Lund University.

“Task 8.4 Enablers Advisory Board (Leader: LUND, Participants: LUND; M1-M48)

The WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board will steer WATERAGRI and support dissemination and communication. This task will focus at bringing together relevant stakeholders not only disseminating the project results but also setting an interactive WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board, made up of a cross-section of representatives critical to the iterative development of WATERAGRI tools and its uptake (representatives from industry). The board will deliver valuable inputs at different stages of the project and provide feedback on solutions as well as discuss challenges and opportunities arising in modernising the water retention and nutrient recycling practice (D8.3). Also, a multi-actor and multi-level engagement approach will be followed aiming at reaching specific audiences covering policy, regulatory, scientific, commercial as well as socio-economic aspects (national ministries, EU and International Agricultural Institutions, policy makers, water retention and nutrient recycling services provides and experts, etc.).

Additionally, this board will further facilitate the effort to establish links to other related projects and activities and disseminate project results. The board’s members will interact with the consortium by participating in plenary project meetings and teleconferences. A non-exclusive preliminary list of to be invited organizations for participation in the Advisory Board is provided in Section 2.2.”

A dedicated deliverable in the form of the report was subsequently introduced:

D8.5 WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board Report (Leader: LUND, R, PU, M12).

The Enablers Advisory Board was introduced to the proposal text in chapter **3.2.1 Overview of the management structure**.

“LUND will coordinate the WATERAGRI project, certifying its previous experience as coordinator and partner of national and international research and development projects. The management structure has been designed on the canvas of the DESCA model which is expected to be the “default setting” for the European Commission, and it has been organized in three main bodies:

- *General assembly (GA): Composed of one representative of each partner of the consortium. Chaired by the project coordinator (PC), as the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium.*
- *Enablers advisory board (EAB): Composed of external senior experts in the field who will give their advice and feedback on the scientific and technical arising issues to the GA.*
- *Executive board (EB): It shall consist of the coordinator and the parties appointed by the GA. The board is responsible for the execution of the project and shall report to and be accountable to the GA.”*

EAB was also mentioned in the proposal text in the chapter **3.2.2. Decision making structure and responsibilities** (page 60).

“Enablers Advisory Board. This board will be appointed and steered by the EB. The EAB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the GA. The renowned researchers in the field from participating universities and other research centres will be invited to participate as members of the EAB. The specific persons to be involved will be defined in the kick-off meeting. The EAB will play a key consultative role in the project. The coordinators will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all parties and each EAB member. Its terms shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in the consortium agreement and it shall be concluded no later than 30 calendar days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier. The project coordinator shall write the minutes of the EAB meetings and prepare the implementation of the EAB's suggestions. The EAB members shall be allowed to participate in GA meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights. The main goals of this board will be:

- *Providing feedback to the project objectives and issues;*
- *Monitoring the milestones of the project, updating their feedback, and providing the necessary inputs;*
- *Providing final feedback on the results and expectations for the future evolution in different sectors; and*
- *Providing scientific expertise when needed.*

One of our preliminary members of the EAB is Dr Marlos De Souza, Secretary – Water Platform, Land and Water Division, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy (agricultural water management; nutrient management, phosphorus and organic matter movement from agricultural land to water via surface runoff). The Finnish Field Drainage Association, Pro Agricultura Seeland, Hungarian Water Cluster, Finnish Seed Potato Centre, EHP Environment and ProAgraria have all promised to send delegates to the EAB. For more preliminary board members, please refer to the letters of support.”

The two-way support between the project and initially contacted potential advisory board members was also expressed through many Letters of Support from institutions like the Finish Field Drainage Association (FFDA, Finland), Pro Agricultura Seeland (PAS, Switzerland), Hungarian Water Cluster

(HWC, Hungary), Finish Seed Potato Centre (FSPC, Finland), EHP Environment (EHP, Finland), ProAgria, Rural Advisory Centre Oulu (ProAgria, Finland). Those institutions were amongst others approached by the Executive Board and invited to nominate their representatives to the WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board on the project implementation stage.

1.2.2 Consortium Agreement

After the project got granted, WATERAGRI consortium members prepared the Consortium Agreement (Version 4, 2020-03-26) with the support of the Enablers Advisory Board according to chapter **6.5 Management Support Team** and subchapter **6.6 Enablers Advisory Board (EAB)** (page 19).

“An Enablers Advisory Board (EAB) will be appointed and steered by the Executive Board and shall be comprised of external senior experts in the field. The EAB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the General Assembly. The Coordinator will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement (attachment 5) is executed between all Parties and each EAB member. Its terms shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in this Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 calendar days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier. The Coordinator shall write the minutes of the EAB meetings and prepare the implementation of the EAB's suggestions. The EAB members shall be allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights.”

The EAB was also mentioned in section **6: Governance Structure**, chapter **6.1 General Structure**:

“The Enablers Advisory Board will assist and facilitate the decisions made by the General Assembly.”

1.2.3 Non-Disclosure Agreement

As an attachment to the Consortium Agreement, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) was introduced for both external stakeholders and the Enablers Advisory Board Members. The following text of the NDA was prepared by LUND's Legal Advisor:

“NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT

THIS NON-DISCLOSURE AGREEMENT (this **“Agreement”**) is entered into on [insert date] 2020 by:

[Insert official name of the visitor or member of the EAB], registration no. [insert reg.no], having its registered office or based in [insert the Legal Address of the Entity] (hereinafter referred to as **the “Recipient”**); and

Lund University, registration no. 202100-3211, having its registered office at P. O. Box 117, SE-221 00 Lund, Sweden, acting on behalf of itself and all other partners (each a “**Partner**”) of the action titled WATER RETENTION AND NUTRIENT RECYCLING IN SOILS AND STREAMS FOR IMPROVED AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION, in short WATERAGRI, with the EU grant reference number 858375, as a part of the Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (the “**Project**”).

Individually referred to as a “**Party**” or collectively as the “**Parties**”.

BACKGROUND

[OPTION 1: *[The Recipient] [The Recipient’s representative [insert name]] has been appointed as a member of the Enablers Advisory Board (“EAB”), which has been established through the consortium agreement between the Partners regarding the Project. As a consequence of the Recipient’s, or its representative’s, role and work in the EAB, certain Confidential Information (as defined below) will be disclosed to the Recipient.]*

[OPTION 2: *[The Recipient] [The Recipient’s representative [insert name]] has been invited to participate as a [guest] in relation to [a meeting] [meetings] within the frame of the Project. As a consequence of the Recipient’s, or its representative’s, participation, certain Confidential Information (as defined below) may be disclosed to the Recipient. [END OF OPTION 2]* The Parties have agreed to enter into this Agreement in order to govern the rights and obligations of the Parties with respect to Confidential Information disclosed in relation to the Project.

CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION

All information of whatever nature and in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Partner (the “**Disclosing Party**”) to the Recipient in connection with the Project during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “**Confidential Information**”.

CONFIDENTIALITY OBLIGATIONS

1. The Recipient hereby undertakes:
 - not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
 - not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;
 - to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
 - to return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on request all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipient including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipient may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy for as long as the copy is retained.

2. *The Recipient shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of its employees, or third parties involved in the Project and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end of the Project and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party.*
3. *The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.*
4. *The Recipient shall promptly advise the Disclosing Party in writing of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.*

EXCEPTIONS

1. *The above shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:*
 - *the Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient's confidentiality obligations;*
 - *the Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential;*
 - *the Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidentiality by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidentiality to the Disclosing Party;*
 - *the Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party;*
 - *the Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure by the Disclosing Party; or*
 - *the Recipient is required to disclose the Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, subject to Section 0.2 hereunder.*
2. *If the Recipient becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it shall, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so, prior to any such disclosure:*
 - *notify the Disclosing Party in writing; and*
 - *comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.*

NO REPRESENTATION OR WARRANTY

The Disclosing Party does not make any representation or warranty as to the accuracy of the Confidential Information and will not have any liability to the Recipient as a result of the Recipient's use of Confidential Information.

NO TRANSFER OF OWNERSHIP

The Parties acknowledge that title to any information disclosed to the Recipient hereunder, including, but not limited to, Confidential Information, and any property rights therein remain the property of the Disclosing Party. The Recipient shall not obtain any proprietary interest in such information through this Agreement. The Recipient is not granted any express or implied licences or other rights to use any information disclosed hereunder for any purpose.

TERM OF THE AGREEMENT

This Agreement shall be effective from the date it has been signed by duly authorized representatives of both Parties and shall remain in force until complete fulfilment of all Partners' obligations in relation to the Project. Notwithstanding the aforementioned, the confidentiality obligations under this Agreement shall remain in force for a period of five (5) years after the date of termination of this Agreement.

GOVERNING LAW

This Agreement shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium excluding its conflict of law provisions.

DISPUTE RESOLUTION

1. *The Parties shall endeavour to settle their disputes amicably. Any dispute, controversy or claim arising under, out of or relating to this Agreement and any subsequent amendments of this Agreement, including, without limitation, its formation, validity, binding effect, interpretation, performance, breach or termination, as well as non-contractual claims, shall be submitted to mediation in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules. The place of mediation shall be Brussels unless otherwise agreed upon. The language to be used in the mediation shall be English unless otherwise agreed upon.*
2. *If, and to the extent that, any such dispute, controversy or claim has not been settled pursuant to the mediation within 60 calendar days of the commencement of the mediation, it shall, upon the filing of a Request for Arbitration by either Party, be referred to and finally determined by arbitration in accordance with the WIPO Expedited Arbitration Rules. Alternatively, if, before the expiration of the said period of 60 calendar days, either Party fails to participate or to continue to participate in the mediation, the dispute, controversy or claim shall, upon the filing of a Request for Arbitration by the other Party, be referred to and finally determined by arbitration in accordance with the WIPO Expedited Arbitration Rules. The place of arbitration shall be Brussels unless otherwise agreed upon. The language to be used in the arbitral proceedings shall be English unless otherwise agreed upon.*
3. *Nothing in this Agreement shall limit the Disclosing Party's right to seek injunctive relief in any applicable competent court.*

[Signatory page below]

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties hereto have caused this Agreement to be executed as of the date stated above.

Date:

Date:

LUND UNIVERSITY**[NAME OF THE RECIPIENT]**

Name:

Name:

Title:

Title:"

2 The main approach

2.1 The strategic approach for using advisory board

After being granted the project, the newly nominated WATERAGRI Executive Board discussed the best strategy of using the Enablers Advisory Board to maximise project impacts and its results. The discussion was being continued on the Management Support Team level by the WATERAGRI Project Coordinator and Project Manager.

Mentioned internal management bodies agreed on the following boundary criteria for the EAB:

- **EXPERIENCE** – The board should preferably consist of expert advisors in the field with the previous or current senior role in leading recognisable institutions.
- **DIVERSITY** – The EAB should represent experts from different fields reinforcing or covering the expertise that is lacking in the WATERAGRI consortium. Its members should also represent different sectors important for the WATERAGRI project like farmers, farmers' association and senior advisors.
- **GENDER BALANCE** – The board should through its nominations undertake all the necessary effort to provide an appropriate gender balance to the EAB board.
- **ADVOCACY** – The EAB will act as an advocate for the subject areas of agricultural water management and nutrient recycling from streams. It should consist of members who will act as Project Ambassadors helping project members establish new contacts with relevant external partners, institutions or projects acting like “door openers” for the WATERAGRI project.

After the first Executive Board meeting, the WATERAGRI project members were informed about the open call for nominations of EAB members. At the same time, the Management Support Team decided to prepare the Terms of Reference for the EAB members to formalise the cooperation and set-up the expectations between parties.

The text of the Terms of the Reference is being currently under negotiation with the EAB members. Its latest version 1.3 is presented below.

“WATERAGRI ENABLERS ADVISORY BOARD

TERMS OF REFERENCE (Terms)

(Draft Version 1.0; Miklas Scholz; 14 September 2020;

Draft Version 1.1; Sebastian Puculek and Miklas Scholz; 15 September 2020;

Draft Version 1.2; Ana Nordberg and Miklas Scholz; 17 September 2020)

Draft Version 1.3; Sebastian Puculek; 4th November 2020;

Purpose

The WATERAGRI consortium established an external Enablers Advisory Board (Board). The Board supports the purpose and aims of the project and will act as an advocate for the subject areas of agricultural water management and nutrient recycling from streams. It will also provide strategic advice on the WATERAGRI project development and on future funding opportunities.

The Board will have a term of office of four years. The Terms and Board membership will be regularly reviewed by the Executive Board to help drive the development of the project beyond its initial start-up phase. The task of the Advisory Board will be to assist in assessing the progress of the project and preparing recommendations for the project Executive Board.–Board members shall not have voting rights, when allowed to participate in General Assembly meetings upon invitation.

The Board members will be appointed by the Executive Board of WATERAGRI. The Board shall be composed of renowned researchers in the relevant field, selected from universities, other research centres and industry. The Board Chair shall be responsible for coordinating the Board work.

Terms

The Terms of the Board shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in the WATERAGRI's Consortium Agreement. The Terms shall be concluded no later than 30 calendar days after each Board member nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged with new member, whichever date is earlier. The Terms for the Board are to:

- 1. To advise on the consortium's strategic direction, focus and priorities in the light of key national and international developments in science, policy and practice*
- 2. To promote the consortium amongst key influencers of national and international policy and practice and potential funders*
- 3. To ensure that the strategic direction and work of WATERAGRI are informed by agricultural practitioners and representatives from related subject areas*
- 4. To advise on the consortium's strategy and where appropriate to promote the relevant subject areas amongst key media and interest groups*
- 5. To advise and where appropriate promote research in agricultural water management and nutrient recycling from streams*
- 6. To advise on the WATERAGRI funding strategy, including identification of potential funding sources, and where appropriate to assist in the process*
- 7. To providing feedback to the project objectives and challenges*
- 8. To provide final feedback on project results and recommendations*
- 9. To provide scientific expertise when required*
- 10. On demand, when asked by the Executive Board, to prepare a recommendation report within 30 days from the request sent by the Project Coordinator to the Board Chair. The Executive Board will formulate the problem in written request and through the Project Coordinator provide the Board Chair with all necessary information, reports, and other materials necessary for preparing the recommendation. The Board Chair will facilitate the report creation within the Advisory Board and submit the recommendation report to the Project Coordinator.*

Frequency of Meetings and Minutes

The intention is to focus on actions that will deliver impact both nationally and internationally. The consortium will minimise the need for physical meetings of the Board requiring international traveling. When possible, the Board meetings will be conducted using virtual means. The Board will meet approximately twice every calendar year. Individual members will be kindly asked to promote and advise the consortium between formal meetings. The Project Coordinator (or its representative) shall write the minutes of the Board meetings and prepare the implementation of the Board's suggestions.

Reimbursement of Board Members

When a physical Board meeting is required, reasonable travel and accommodation expenses will be reimbursed upon written request to the WATERAGRI Coordinator. Reimbursement rules can be obtained from the Project Manager.

Chair of the Board

Lund University will nominate for the first Board meeting senior persons of high trust and responsibility. The Board will subsequently elect a Chair during their first meeting. The term of office will initially be two years. The selection for the next Chair of the Board will take place during the 4th General Assembly meeting. All Board representatives and Executive Board members can nominate the incoming Chair two months prior to the 4th General Assembly meeting. Each Board and Executive Board member can only nominate one person. Each Executive Board member and Advisory Board member have one vote. The selection of the Chair of the Board will be done by secret ballot with use of digital tools. The results of the voting will be accessible to all voting members.

Ethics and Gender Advisor to WATERAGRI

Lund University will nominate for the first Board meeting a person of high trust that could potentially serve as an Ethics and Gender Advisor for WATERAGRI. The Board will subsequently elect an independent Ethics and Gender Advisor to the WATERAGRI consortium during their first meeting.

Annual Report

The Board will be asked to comment in written on WATERAGRI progress reports and impact reviews of work packages.

The following reports are planned to be submitted during the project duration:

Internal reporting:

- 1) Mid-Term review (Apr 2022)*
- 2) 1st scientific report (Jul 2021)*
- 3) 2nd scientific report (Jul 2022)*
- 4) 3rd scientific report Jul 2023)*

Mandatory EC reporting:

- 1) 1st Technical report (Oct 2021)
- 2) 2nd Technical report (Apr 2023)
- 3) 3rd Technical report (Apr 2024)

Members of the Board

The Board is composed of external senior experts in the field who will give their advice and feedback on the scientific, technical and socio-economic issues arising to the General Assembly of WATERAGRI. The Board will play a key consultative role in the project. The Coordinator (or his representative) will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement between all parties and each Board member is signed. The current members of the Board are as follows:"

2.2 Composition of the Board

WATERAGRI members contacted selected individuals meeting the EAB criteria specified in chapter 2.1. The current composition of the EAB is presented below:

Farmers:

Henrik Djerv, Federation of Swedish Farmers

Otto von Arnold, Jordberga Farm

Peter Krantz, Loarp Farm

Farming associations:

Helena Äijö, Representative of The Finnish Field Drainage Association

Riina Rahkila, Representative of ProAgria

Risto Hiljanen, Representative of EHP Environment

Senior Advisors:

Dr Nidhi Nagabhatla is a Principal Researcher: Water Security at UNU INWEH. She also leads the capacity development program at the institute. With over 20 years of experience as a systems science specialist, she led, coordinated and implemented transdisciplinary projects on water and wetlands, and worked with multi-disciplinary researcher teams in various geographical regions (Asia, South Africa, Western Europe and Canada). She served with leading institutes such as the International Water Management Institute (IWMI), World Fish Centre and IUCN shaping their research and capacity development initiatives. She is affiliated with Oxford University (UK), Leibniz University (Germany) and McMaster

University (Canada) on sustainability research and science-policy interfacing. Dr Nagabhatla published close to 200 research papers and serves on editorial and review committees of several international journals, most of which are available at https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nidhi_Nagabhatla.

A book she recently co-edited entitled [Multifunctional Wetlands – Pollution Abatement and Other Ecological Services from Natural and Constructed Wetlands](#) provide a comprehensive synthesis of both the opportunities and the challenges associated with nature-based solutions.

To know more about her academic and professional background and affiliations, please see <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nidhi-nagabhatla-3450885/>.

Dr Floor Brouwer is an environmental economist at Wageningen Research in The Netherlands, working as a senior research scholar in the research areas green economy and land use. He holds a PhD in economics from the Free University in Amsterdam for a study on integrated economic-ecological modelling. His research is focussed on the efficient use of natural resources in European agriculture. He is scientific co-ordinator of the H2020 project ‘Sustainable Integrated Management for the Nexus of water-land-food-energy-climate for a resource efficient Europe’ (Research & Innovation Action, 2016-2020) and of the H2020 project ‘Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture’ (SUPREMA) (Coordination and Support Action, 2018-2020). He is also leading the Nexus Project Cluster, a group of some 25 independent water/energy/food cross-sector research initiatives, which team-up to increase communication and dissemination of the nexus resulting in enhanced impact.

Dr Marek Mróz is an Associate Professor at the University of Warmia and Mazury, Faculty of Geodesy, Geospatial and Civil Engineering. He is also an Associate Professor at the Polish Air Force University, Faculty of Aeronautics, Department of Air Navigation. His main directions of activity are integration of Pol-In-SAR satellite data with hyperspectral data in research on the natural environment and thematic cartography.

Membership of professional bodies: Committee of Geodesy of the Polish Academy of Science (2011-2020) – elected member. Technical Committee TC 297 for Geographic Information of Polish Committee for Standardization (2009-2016) - member. National Science Centre; Physical Sciences and Engineering/Expert Board ST_10 - Earth system science - member (since 2011), Polish Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing – Council member (2013-2016, 2017-2020).

Dr Stefanakis is an Assistant Professor at the School of Environmental Engineering, Technical University of Crete, Greece. He is the Regional Coordinator for Africa and Middle East of the Specialist Group ‘Wetlands for Water Pollution Control’ of the International Water Association. He is the Editor-in-Chief of the journal ‘Circular Economy and Sustainability’ and Associate Editor of other scientific journals. He is an environmental engineer and researcher focusing on water engineering and specifically on nature-based solutions and ecological engineering. He is an expert on sustainable and decentralized water and wastewater treatment systems. He has designed, managed and constructed several ecological wastewater treatment facilities across Europe, Middle East, Africa, USA and South America. In the past, he worked as researcher and Lecturer at the University of Brighton in the UK, the University of Beira Interior in Portugal, the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ in Germany, and the Democritus University of Thrace in Greece. His publication record includes articles in international scientific journals and conference proceedings, as well as books and several book chapters. He is known in the related international fields as an enthusiast of green technologies for water management and reuse, always trying to promote and disseminate such technologies and transfer his knowledge to young engineers and students.

Dr sc. agr. Iris Kormann is an agroecologist with experience in ecosystem services (pollination and pest control), agroecology, toxicology as well as project coordination, knowledge transfer, and student supervision. After her MSc in Biology at the University of Tübingen, Germany, she conducted a PhD in Agroecology at the Georg-August University Göttingen, Germany. After graduation, she worked as a post-doc at the Pollinator Health Extension Group, Oregon State University, for Nature Conservation and Landscape Ecology, University of Freiburg, Germany, and the Institute of Bee Health, Bern University, Switzerland. Currently, she works for ProAgricultura Seeland in Switzerland. *“I feel fortunate to work for the ProAgricultura and help to promote sustainable, productive land management. I am relatively new to the topic of sustainable water management, but I am looking forward to dive into the topic and work closely with farmers, scientists and organisations.”*

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Iris_Kormann_Nee_Motzke

2.3 Making use of EAB

The composition of the board comprising senior experts is based on strategic decisions. Relations with the Enablers Advisory Board can be conducted in two ways: formally by official recommendations to the WATERAGRI Executive Board as described in the WATERAGRI Enablers Advisory Board Terms of Reference or semi-formal established externally by EAB members. In the latter case, for example, the WATERAGRI Project Coordinator was approached by the EAB member Riina Rahkila to establish a strategic cooperation with the “Environmentally Wise Farmer 2020-2022” project. The project aims to develop environmentally wise agricultural measures in co-operation with farmers, advisors and researchers in the area of Northern Ostrobothnia.

At the time of drawing up this deliverable, the Executive Board did not decide to go officially for the Recommendation Report (EAB Terms of Reference).

EAB members are invited to every WATERAGRI event including General Assembly meetings. EAB members and the rules of approaching the EAB was presented to all WATERAGRI Executive Board members and project partners during the 2nd Executive Board and the 2nd General Assembly meetings (hosted by UOULU).

Future EAB activities will consist of selecting the EAB Chair and organising the first EAB meeting with the WATERAGRI Executive Board members.